

SUBSURFACE DAMAGE MEASUREMENT ON CARBON CARBON COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN BRAKING APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY : This paper deals with the measurement of subsurface damage of composite materials after braking solicitations. Several carbon carbon composites materials are studied. They have been tested under industrial braking conditions. Different damage methods are also used to estimate the braking effects on the mechanical behavior of these materials. In particular, a meso-hardness test is adapted to the heterogeneity of carbon carbon composite and to their porosity. Depending on the type of material, the results show the evolution of the meso-harness as a function of the distance to the braking surface. In the case of the quasi transverse isotropic behavior, we obtain a measurement of a damaged subsurface. An other original compression-bending test is also used, which confirms this damaged subsurface effect before wear occurs.

KEYWORDS: carbon-carbon, braking, wear, subsurface, damage, hardness, compression

INTRODUCTION

Carbon carbon materials present a good mechanical behavior under specific conditions as high temperature. Besides, their low density is a main quality used for manufacturing brake discs of heavy vehicles as planes or trains. In this case, the braking system is made of several carbon carbon discs which are rubbing one against another - rotor against stator. Three different carbon carbon composites have been tested under industrial conditions as braking to a stop, and with neutral, wet or usual environment. Recalling the main results of thermal and wear behavior, we develop here experiments on CC composite materials after series of braking tests in order to measure the braking effects on the composite subsurface. For homogeneous materials, several authors show the deterioration of the material, with plasticity or microcraks, in proximity of the damaged surface [1], [2], [3]. Then we develop specific tests to quantify a possible damage during and after wear (braking) solicitations.

CARBON CARBON COMPOSITE MATERIALS AND BRAKING

Description

Three carbon carbon composites materials are compared here [4].

Material A : Carbon carbon laminates with thick woven layers in different directions in the disc plane. This material presents a quasi isotropic behavior in this plane.

Material B : Carbon carbon laminates with long fibers in a random distribution in the disc plane. As material A, this one presents a similar isotropic behavior in this plane.

Material C : Tridirectional carbon carbon composite material with needle bonding normal to the disc and presenting an orthotropic behavior.

Thermal and Wear Behavior

During the braking tests, Jeanne [5] measures the disc temperature and the wear rate. The main test characteristics are: a normal pressure of 1.3 MPa and angular velocity of 365 rad.s^{-1} . With these parameters, the surface energy density reaches 300 J/cm^2 . An example of temperature evolution is given in Fig. 1 (material B). The measurements are realized at distance of 1 mm, 3.5 mm and 6 mm to the friction surface. The highest temperature varies with the type of environment up to 1000°C with the experimental conditions. In the same way, the thermal gradient varies too and presents a low variation under wet environment.

Fig. 1: Temperature evolution (material B) and wear rate of carbon carbon composites (A, B and C) during braking

Fig. 2: Mechanical behavior (material A) and damage in compression test

The whole wear rate after different braking tests are presented below. For each material, this higher wear rate does not occur for the same environment. That shows the great complexity of the phenomena associated with thermal, chemical and mechanical processes [7], [8], [9], [10].

Modeling of the Mechanical Behavior

The three carbon carbon composite materials present a similar macroscopical behavior. Fig. 2 shows a characteristic compression behavior (material A) in the disc plane with cyclic loading and unloading to free stress. They present an elasto plastic behavior with a linear damage evolution.

As we can see in Fig. 3, the Young modulus normal to the disc plan is very small. The in plane elastic behavior is determined by :

$$\varepsilon_{ii}^e = \sigma_{ii} / E_{ii}^0(1 - d_i)$$

with $i=1,2$ and $d_i=1-E_i/E_i^0$

The damage evolution is described by :

$$d = f(\sigma^s) = (\sigma^s - \sigma^e) / b \quad \text{with : } \sigma^s = \sup_{\tau \leq t} |\sigma|$$

Beside a typical non linear modeling is obtained by the equations :

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_p = \dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial g}{\partial \sigma} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{p} = -\dot{\lambda} \frac{\partial g}{\partial L}$$

where g is the coupled plastic criterion : $g(\tilde{\sigma}) = \tilde{\sigma}_{II} - L(p)$ with : $\tilde{\sigma} = s/(1-D)$ and L the hardening function which must be identified for each material.

	$E_1=E_2$ (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	σ_e (MPa)	b (MPa)	$d_{critique}$	$\varepsilon_{rupture}$ (%)	$\varepsilon_{pl.rupt.}$ (%)	$\sigma_{rupture}$ (MPa)
Material A	30	1	20	137,5	0,7	0,9	0,15	75
Material B	32	0,7	10	66,7	0,6	0,52	0,075	50
Material C	18	1,25	20	44,5	0,45	1,18	0,1	40

Fig. 3: Mechanical characteristics of CC

MESO-HARDNESS

A specific meso-hardness test is developed here taking into account the particular geometry of the three carbon carbon materials. A spherical indenter is chosen and optimized. Its diameter must be proportional to the surface elementary cell size in order to measure the meso-hardness corresponding to the homogeneous behavior and not the meso-hardness of the constituents. The carbon carbon samples are then machined with a succession of steps whose thickness is 0.05 mm. For each step we measure twelve meso-hardness under progressive loading. The mass used in the test are 0.3 kg, 1 kg and 15 kg. The optimal diameter of the spherical tip is 6.35 mm. Each test lasts about one minute.

During the meso-hardness test, the indenter penetrates the sample in a very small thickness, much smaller than the thickness of a fiber layer. In that case, it is possible to obtain the evolution of the meso-hardness in the material, due to the braking solicitations.

The results are analyzed with two classical concepts of hardness : HB is the Brinell hardness taking into account the permanent or plastic deformation of the material under loading : h_p . HR is the Rockwell hardness taking into account the total deformation, id est the elasto-plastic deformation of the material under the indenter : h_{ep} .

With F, the load, D, the diameter of spherical tip and d the diameter of the indentation area, we have :

$$HB = \frac{F}{\pi D h_p} , \quad HR = \frac{F}{\pi D h_{ep}} , \quad h_{ep} = [D - (D^2 - d^2)^{1/2}] / 2$$

The measure of h_p is obtained during the test with unloading to free stress.

Results are presented in Fig. 4a, 4b and 4c.

Material A : The meso-hardness from the braking surface to the middle of the sample describes a periodical evolution where the periodic distance is equal to the thickness of the fiber woven layers. It is difficult to observe a particular evolution of the hardness near the braking surface.

Material C : The hardness evolution does not present a characteristic variation between the surface and the middle of the sample. We note that the accuracy of the results is not good. That is an indicator of the heterogeneity of this material coming from the needle bonding normal to the disc plane.

Material B : The results are presented here in term of damage, with D a scalar parameter equal to the ratio of the meso-hardness in the middle of the sample and the local meso-hardness [6], [4].

$$D = 1 - \frac{H}{H^*}$$

Lemaître [6] showed a similar evolution of the damage measure by classical tests as tension test $D=1-E/E_0$ and hardness test $D=1-H/H^*$ for isotropic material. If E_0 represents the initial Young's modulus, the meso-hardness H^* is more complex to obtain. In the case of an elastoplastic behavior with hardening, the damage must appear at the same time as hardening.

So, if H represents the hardness of the material after loading, and H_0 the hardness before loading, we should obtain :

$$H > H_0 \text{ with } H_0 = k \sigma_p , \quad H = k (R + \sigma_p) (1 - D) ,$$

R is the hardening variable and σ_p the plastic low threshold stress.

The measure of damage must be so :

$D = 1 - \frac{H}{H^*}$ with $H^* = k(R + \sigma_p)$ hardness of the material with hardening but without damage, obtained by calculus. For the carbon carbon composite material B under braking solicitation, we observe a hardness H at the surface smaller than H_0 in the middle of the sample, $H < H_0$. That means that damage appears without hardening, this phenomenon is similar to the damage evolution in elastic fatigue test for isotropic metals. Consequently, we propose the hypothesis that under braking solicitations, appears a damage evolution mainly due to thermal and physicochemical phenomena, and without hardening.

Fig. 4: Meso hardness ((a) and (b)) and damage (c)

The model of damage measurement is then :

$$D = 1 - \frac{H}{H^*}$$

with $H^* = k \sigma_p$ and $H = k \sigma_p (1 - D)$

The damage evolution shows a decreasing from the surface of the material.

In the middle of the disc, the variation of measurement ΔH corresponds to the heterogeneity of the carbon carbon with a relative ratio : $\Delta H/\Delta H^* = 7.5\%$.

Near the surface, the ratio $\Delta H/\Delta H^*$ measured reaches 20%. Between 7.5% and 20%, it is possible to consider this ratio as a measurement of damage in a subsurface of this carbon carbon composite material. The depth of this subsurface is $a=0.4 \pm 0.1$ mm. The thickness of this damaged subsurface will probably vary as a function of the nature of the braking solicitation (frequency, energy level...). In case of very dissipate braking, the damaged subsurface will disappear in wear.

COMPRESSION BENDING TEST

The brake discs in material B are damaged only in a small thickness near the surface. We tried to define a macroscopical test sensitive to a variation on rigidity in the subsurface. The principle of this test is shown in Fig. 6a and 6b. Parallelepipedic samples are taken out of the brake discs after braking test.

If a sample is not damaged, its rigidity center and its geometrical center match each other in a cross section. If not, appears a distance between these two points, that generates a bending couple when the sample is loaded in compression. Using strain gauges in all the lateral surfaces of the sample, it is possible to measure the bending effect due to the damaged subsurface. A specific experimental setup (Fig. 6b) is then constructed in order to apply the compression load with a good accuracy (0.01 mm) exactly in the center of the cross-section. A steel ball permits the free rotation of the head sample.

Fig. 6: Samples and compression-bending setup

This experimental setup has been tested on model materials for which a subsurface with a different rigidity was prepared and then well known. Its accuracy permits to detect a damaged subsurface with the following characteristics : $a.d = 0.02$ mm with a : the thickness of the damaged zone and d : the mean damage in this subsurface.

With E_i , the Young modulus of the CC sample in the compression direction, and $l/2-\alpha$ the distance between the center of rigidity and the center of the cross section, we can write :

$$\int_s E_i(x - \alpha) dS = 0 \tag{1}$$

Suppose that the damage evolution is linear, as shown with the meso-hardness results, we obtain :

$$\begin{aligned} E_i(x) &= E_i^0(1-d(x)) && \text{for } x \in [1-a, 1] \\ \text{and } E_i(x) &= E_i^0 && \text{for } x \in [0, 1-a]. \end{aligned}$$

Assume too that :

$$E_i(x) = E_i^0 [1 + d_c[(1-x)/a - 1]]$$

Fig. 7: Identification of the damaged depth

It means that the critical damage is obtained at the braking surface, so previous relation (1), could be written :

$$2\alpha = (d_m a(a-2l) + l^2) / (1 - d_m a)$$

Note that this scalar equation permits only to obtain one scalar unknown, the measure of α by the rotation of the head sample permits to find the thickness of the damaged subsurface. The results of this compression bending test are shown in Fig. 7.

All specimens in material B present a bending effect corresponding to the values of a and d : $a \cdot d_m = 0.05$ mm

Then if we consider a linear evolution of the damage in the subsurface, with a critical damage $d_c=0.2$ measured with the meso-hardness results, we obtain a thickness of this subsurface equal to $a=0.35$ mm.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Note that the measure of the bending effect must be absolutely realized in the beginning of the rotation. If not, a complementary bending couple appears due to the progressive lateral displacement of the setup induced by the bending strains.

The both results of meso-hardness and compression bending test developed here are in good agreement. They show that, for the carbon carbon composite materials B, it can exist a damaged subsurface induced by specific braking solicitations. Naturally, this subsurface is progressively turning into wear particles, during a braking test. However, it seems to be necessary to take into account the real damaged behavior of materials in order to have a better understanding of their surface deterioration. The main difficulties which limit these approach are the heterogeneity of carbon carbon composites and their porosity, which stop us developing others methods to measure this subsurface.

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